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The Impact of Digital Transformation Strategy on the Innovation Performance of Commercial Banks in China

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Abstract

The theoretical research model for this study aims to elucidate the intricate relationships between digital transformation strategy, dynamic capabilities, Information Technology Infrastructure (ITI), and innovation performance within commercial banks. Based on research into dynamic capabilities, this study identifies three critical capabilities that are essential for effectively leveraging digital transformation strategies: sensing capability, seizing capability, and reconfiguration capability. Sensing capability involves identifying and assessing opportunities in the environment; seizing capability pertains to mobilizing resources to capture these opportunities; and reconfiguration capability refers to the continuous alignment and realignment of resources and processes to sustain competitive advantage. As a result, IT infrastructure optimization not only improves operational efficiency but also drives strategic growth, positioning banks to meet the challenges and opportunities of a digital-first world.

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